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3 **Abundance and reproductive patterns of the excavating sponge *Cliona vermifera*: a**
4 **potential new threat to Pacific coral reefs**
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For Peer Review

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3 **ABSTRACT:** *Cliona vermifera* is a common excavating sponge in reefs from the East Pacific.
4 Preliminary observations have suggested that the sponge apparently has increased its aggressiveness
5 against living corals in recent years. However, the lack of information on about the demographic and
6 reproductive traits of this sponge prevents any reliable assessment of the ongoing situation. Abundance
7 and reproductive patterns of the sponge in a Mexican Pacific coral reef over a 4-year period (2007-2010)
8 are herein described for the first time. A 2-way ANOVA revealed that infestation was significantly
9 higher in living coral colonies (34.8%) than in rubble (13.7%). It also indicated that incidence of
10 infestation did not progressively increase over the years, but rather peaked significantly, yet transiently,
11 in 2008. It was estimated that 60 to 85% of sponges in the population engaged in sexual reproduction
12 annually, leading to considerable reproductive output. The sponge proved gonochoristic, with a sex ratio
13 strongly departing from parity (1 male: 3 females). Oogenesis developed at least two oocyte cohorts
14 from March to November, at densities of up to 3.5 oocytes per mm² of tissue. Spermatogenesis lasted
15 about a month, but often producing more than a pulse from July to November, coupled with peaks of
16 oocyte maturation. Fertilization occurred internally to produce encapsulated zygotes that were rapidly
17 released in one or more pulse from July to November. No gametic activity occurred in the sponges from
18 December to February, which was the period of lowest temperature (~18.5-20 °C). Because anomalous
19 temperature rises, that are detrimental to corals, do not appear to negatively affect the reproduction and
20 abundance of *C. vermifera*, it is likely that the excavating activity of this sponge may be compromising
21 coral reefs health since they are recurrently affected by episodes of thermal stress.
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38 **Keywords:** *Excavating sponges, invertebrate reproduction, coral reefs, bleaching, Pocillopora.*
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INTRODUCTION

Many reefs in the East Pacific have lost their frame-building corals as a result of past ENSO events (Glynn 1990), upwelling events (Hernández et al. 2010), and various anthropogenic impacts (Nava and Ramírez-Herrera 2011). After those impacts, abundance of excavating sponges has been reported to increase in the affected ecosystems (Rützler 2002; Schönberg and Ortiz 2008; Carballo et al. 2013). Recent studies also show that bioerosion is not only linked to anomalous environmental conditions, but also to specific values of skeletal density of the affected corals (Hernández-Ballesteros et al. 2013). This realization may have major implications for the future of reef structures, because bioerosion by excavating sponges would be facilitated in a global context of ocean acidification (Hoegh-Guldberg et al. 2007; Wisshak et al. 2012).

Excavating sponges belonging to the family Clionidae D'Orbigny, 1851 are very diverse in East Pacific coral reefs (Carballo et al. 2004, 2007, 2008). Along the Mexican Pacific coast, twenty-three species have been identified to date (Cruz-Barraza et al. 2011), with *Cliona vermifera* Hancock, 1849 the most common excavator in corals of the genera *Pocillopora*, *Porites* and *Pavona* (Carballo et al. 2008, 2013). Usually, only a small portion of the *C. vermifera* body (i.e., 0.3 to 1.2 mm in diameter, red bright papillae) is noticed by reef divers, but the sponge has the ability to burrow by dissolving the calcium carbonate matrix, so that the bulk of the body extends through a complex network of reticulate galleries and chambers, eventually filling entirely the interior of infested coral branches. This sponge has been shown to reach a bioeroding rate of $4.5 \pm 0.9 \text{ kg CaCO}_3\text{m}^{-2} \text{ year}^{-1}$ that is close to the coral calcification rate per unit of area (Nava and Carballo 2008). Thus, any factor enhancing sponge excavating activity and/or decreasing coral calcification rates may trigger a significant imbalance in the accretion/destruction ratio of the many Pacific reefs where this sponge abounds.

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3 In recent years, there have been signs that suggest a potential increase in the infestation of living
4 corals by *C. vermifera* (Carballo et al. 2013). Nevertheless, risk assessment is impossible because there
5 is virtually no quantifiable information available about abundance patterns and life history, either for
6 this species or for any other *Cliona* spp. in the entire American Pacific. Through a quantification of the
7 infestation levels of different coral substrata and through an evaluation of the reproductive potential of
8 the sponge, this study presents the first assessment of the potential threat that *Cliona vermifera*
9 represents to Pacific Mexican reefs.
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20 21 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

22 23 **Sponge abundance and coral infestation levels**

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25 The study was conducted in a coral community located in a semi-closed bay at Isabel Island
26 (21°52'30" N, 105° 54'54" W; Mexico, Pacific Ocean). The corals abounded along each side of the bay.
27 Interlocking coral branches of *Pocillopora* species have built a discontinuous reef framework consisting
28 of small platforms (1 to 3 m wide) characterized by ample zones of exposed carbonate substrate, with
29 numerous living coral colonies established at their upper surface.
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38 To monitor sponge abundance in this reef system, three 50 m-long transects were set randomly on the
39 study area each month during 2007, 2008 and 2010. Along each transect, a coral rubble (CR), and a
40 complete branch of a living coral colony (LC) adjacent to the transect line were collected approximately
41 every 2 meters by scuba diving, yielding 25 pieces per substratum type (CR, LC) and transect. All the
42 collected substrata were broken into small pieces in the laboratory, examining the inside for the presence
43 of the excavating sponge. This species can unequivocally be identified taxonomically by its papillae and
44 skeletal features (Carballo et al. 2004).
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55 The incidence of infestation (%) for a given substratum type at a given time was estimated by pooling
56 data on the presence/absence of *C. vermifera* to obtain monthly average (\pm SD). Differences in incidence
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3 of infestation (%), as a function of substratum type (LC vs. RC) and time (2007, 2008, and 2010), were
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5 analyzed using a two-way ANOVA on untransformed, normal, and homoscedastic data. To further
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7 identify groups responsible for the differences, pairwise multiple comparisons were conducted following
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9 the Holm-Sidak method. Although the ANOVA was initially designed for each month to provide a
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11 datum (N =12), in 2007 we failed to collect transect data in January and March. Consequently, data from
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13 those months were also eliminated for 2008 and 2010 prior to analysis. This procedure decreased
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15 replication (N= 10), yet it allowed the balanced data set required for a reliable two-way ANOVA (power
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17 for factor "Substratum"= 1; power for factor "Time"= 0.62; power for "Substratum x Time"= 0.05).
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23 As our team had been working in the study area during 2005 and 2006 and had conducted some
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25 preliminary transects (June and October 2005; March, June, October, and November 2006) to initially
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27 evaluate infestation levels of living coral and rubble by *C. vermifera*, average infestation prior to 2007
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29 was inferred by pooling data from all those previous transects. This initial data set (< 2007) was not
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31 considered for the 2-way ANOVA but served as a tentative reference value, which plotted in the
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33 ANOVA graphic output, should inform about the approximate abundance of *C. vermifera* in living
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35 corals and rubble immediately prior to the onset of this study. Furthermore, to statistically explore if
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37 these previous data could help to decide whether an increase in the sponge aggressiveness against living
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39 corals could have occurred in the last years, an unbalance one-way ANOVA was conducted for data on
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41 infestation (%) of living coral. In this analysis, it was included every month with transect data during
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43 2005 (N=2), 2006 (N=4), 2007 (N=10), 2008 (N= 12) and 2010 (N= 12). Data passed normality (p=
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45 0.472) and homoscedasticity (p= 0.842) tests, but unequally low replication for years 2005 and 2006
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47 favored a low power in the ANOVA (power of test= 0.05), so that the results has to be taken cautiously.
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Reproductive cycle and seawater temperature

The reproductive cycle of *C. vermifera* was investigated by sampling tissue monthly, from April 2007 to November 2010. Each month, 10 *Pocillopora verrucosa* colonies infested by *C. vermifera* were selected randomly and a branch was collected. Sponge tissue pieces were dissected and fixed in 4% formalin, decalcified in 5% nitric acid for 2 h, rinsed in distilled water, and desilicified with 5% hydrofluoric acid for 1.5 h. Samples were dehydrated in a graded ethanol series (70, 80, 90 and 100 %), cleared in xylene, and embedded in paraffin, following standard protocols (e.g., Riesgo et al. 2007). Five-micron thick sections were obtained using a Leica RM2125RT rotary microtome (Leica Microsystems, Nussloch, Germany). Sections were stained with hematoxylin–eosin–Mayer, and mounted onto glass slides. They were examined for the presence of reproductive elements (i.e., spermatid cysts, oocytes, and zygotes) with a Leica D3000 compound microscope (Leica Microsystems, Paderborn, Germany) equipped with a Leica DFC295 color digital camera. Following the methodology in Riesgo and Maldonado (2008), cytological counts were conducted using a minimal area of 5.7 mm² of tissue sample. Digital images served to measure size of spermatid cysts, oocytes and zygotes over time, as well as the abundance (mean density \pm SD) of these various reproductive elements per tissue unit area. To determine oocyte diameters only sections intersecting the cell nucleus were considered (n=25 per individual and month). Spermatid cysts, which in this species were nearly spherical, were measured (n=25 per individual and month) across their largest diameter.

To conduct scanning electron microscopy (SEM) observations, small tissue pieces of individuals in reproduction were fixed in 2.5% glutaraldehyde for 3 h, rinsed in distilled water, and dehydrated in a graded ethanol series. Subsequently, samples were critical-point dried using liquid carbon dioxide as a transient medium, mounted on glass stubs, air-dried, and sputter-coated with gold–palladium before

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3 observation using a JEOL JSM-5300 scanning electron microscope (Akishima, Tokyo, Japan) operating
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5 at 15.0 kV.
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9 To examine the potential relationship of temperature with the timing and abundance of
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11 reproductive elements, we recorded seawater temperature every 6 h for the entire study period using a
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13 HOBO data logger (Onset Computer Corporation, Bourne, MA, USA) placed at a depth of 6 m. Monthly
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15 averaged temperature values were plotted against monthly averaged values of abundance for the various
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17 reproductive elements (i.e., oocytes, spermatid cyst, and zygotes). Spearman's rank correlation was also
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19 used to assess relationships between temperature and 1) percentage of reproductive individuals, 2)
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21 abundance of reproductive elements, and 3) size of the reproductive elements.
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29 Results

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32 **Sponge abundance:** When all transects available for years 2005, 2006, 2007, 2008, 2010 were
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34 considered, *Cliona vermifera* was found to infest 24.2 ± 14.2 % of the examined substrata, including
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36 both rubble and living corals. A 2-way ANOVA revealed that average infestation varied with
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38 Substratum factor ($p < 0.001$; Fig. 1a), found in living coral ($34.8 \pm 9.9\%$) nearly 3-times higher than in
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40 rubble (12.4 ± 7.3 %). Average incidence of infestation also varied with Time factor ($p = 0.016$), being
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42 significantly higher in 2008 than in 2007 and 2010, two years which were not significantly different
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44 from each other (Fig. 1a). The magnitude of the increase of infestation during 2008 similarly affected
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46 both living coral and coral rubble, which showed parallel trends in this regard during the study period
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48 (Fig. 1a), as confirmed by a non-significant ($p = 0.821$) "Substratum x Time" interaction in the ANOVA.
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54 A visual comparison (Fig. 1a) between the robust 2007-2010 data and occasional transects
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56 irregularly collected during 2005 and 2006 (i.e., <2007) suggests that, in global terms, the
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3 aggressiveness of *C. vermifera* against living coral has not increased substantially over the last 6 years,
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5 slightly shifting from the 30.7 ± 8.3 % collectively estimated for the period 2005-2006 (i.e., <2007) to
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7 the 34.8 ± 9.9 % averaged for the 2007-2010 period. A tentative, unbalanced one-way ANOVA
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9 considering all transects measured in 2005, 2006, 2007, 2008 and 2010 (Fig. 1b) concluded that
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11 between-year differences in infestation (%) of living corals was statistically non-significant ($p < 0.497$),
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13 despite an apparent progressive increase from 2005 to 2008. Similarly, when data for 2010 were
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15 eliminated from the analysis for exploratory purposes, the ANOVA did not detect significant differences
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17 between years.
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22 23 24 **Sponge reproductive cycle**

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26 *Cliona vermifera* was gonochoristic. Between 60 and 85 % of the sponge individuals appeared to
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28 engage in sexual reproduction over a year cycle, as indicated by data from those months when gametes
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30 became mature (Figs. 2, 3, 4). Sex ratio departed from parity, with females being about 3 times more
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32 frequent than males. Females were easy to identify cytologically, because oocytes were very obvious
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34 cells in the tissue (Fig. 5b-d). Early oocytes detected in the mesohyl were spherical or ovate, measured
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36 ~ 10.5 μm in diameter and showed a nucleolated nucleus as well as small yolk bodies in their cytoplasm.
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38 Matures oocytes were spherical, 60-90 μm in diameter, with a comparatively larger nucleus (15-20 μm)
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40 and abundant yolk bodies filling the cytoplasm (Fig. 5d). Unlike females, male sponges were difficult to
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42 detect, as spermatogenesis was a quite rapid process, and spermatocysts did not occurred in the tissue
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44 for much longer than a month (Figs. 2, 3, 4). These reproductive elements were spherical or slightly
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46 oval, often ranging from 60 to 120 μm across its largest axis (Fig. 5e-f). Each mature cyst contained
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48 numerous 2-2.5 μm headed spermatozoa, provided with a 30 μm long flagellum (Fig. 5h). Cysts
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50 experienced synchronous development and spermatozoa showed no apparent spatial pattern of
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3 arrangement (Fig. 5h), other than showing the flagellum consistently directed towards the lumen of the
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cysts.

In females, oocytes formed at least two cohorts, the first typically becoming mature around June and the second around November, as indicated by the high percentage of individuals engaged in gametogenesis in those months (Fig. 2), the time course of oocyte density in the tissue (Fig. 3), and the time course of oocyte size (Fig. 3). Two pulses of spermatogenesis closely coupled to peaks of oocyte maturation in June and November were detected in 2008 and 2009 (Figs. 2, 3, 4). The highest spermatogenic cyst density occurred in the spring of each year (0.68, 0.19 and 0.52 spermatogenic cyst mm⁻², respectively), almost concomitantly with maximum oocytes densities (Fig. 3). In 2010, both oogenesis and spermatogenesis apparently produced 3 coupled pulses, during August, September, and October (Figs. 2, 3). In 2005, we failed to detect spermatogenesis, probably due to an initial inappropriate sampling strategy for such a rapid process and to insufficient familiarization of the team with the reproductive cytology of this sponge. This made the reproductive quantification of male gametic activity for 2005 to be taken cautiously.

We never captured any event of sperm release "in situ" and cannot discard that they took place at night time or at ~~the~~ sunrise. It was noticed that as in other *Cliona* spp., fertilization occurred internally (Maldonado and Riesgo 2008; Piscitelli et al. 2011), since we never found embryos that were being brooded in the tissue. Rather, fertilized oocytes (i.e., zygotes) became rapidly enclosed by an organic, capsule-like envelope (Fig. 5h) and were released readily to the water column (one or two days) after fertilization for initial cleavage and subsequent external development. Due to the brevity of the zygote residence within the sponge body, zygotes were evasive to our monthly sampling and were captured only once over the study, in November 2009.

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4 It is worth noting that, after the November peak of zygote release, gametic activity consistently
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6 ceased in the population from December to February, coincidentally with the coldest period of the year
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8 (Figs. 2, 3, 4). Indeed, although annual temperature shifts were moderate at the tropical latitude of the
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10 study area (yearly minimum and maximum being 21- 24°C and 30-31°C, respectively, depending on the
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12 year), seawater temperature appears to have an important role in the reproductive cycle of this sponge.
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14 After gametogenesis pause in the cold months, oogenesis was resumed around April, coincidentally with
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16 the onset of rising of seawater temperature (Figs. 2, 3, 4). Likewise, the density of oocytes increased
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18 significantly with an increase in water temperature ($r = 0.6$, $p < 0.05$; Fig. 3), the highest average
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20 densities (2.14, 1.61, 2.18 and 3.40 oocytes mm^{-2} for 2007 to 2010, respectively) occurred coincidentally
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22 with maxima in seawater temperature ($\sim 28\text{-}30\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$). Similarly, the size of oocytes during their growth
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24 also correlated with water temperature values ($r = 0.5$, $p < 0.05$; Fig. 4).
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Discussion

The finding that close to 34% of living colonies of *Pocillopora* spp. were invaded by *Cliona vermifera* confirms previous suspicions that this sponge is an important bioeroder in coral reefs of the Mexican Pacific (Carballo et al. 2013). The excavating activity leads, in many instances, to the destruction of a large portion of the internal calcium-carbonate matrix of the coral branches (Fig. 5a), making the colonies fragile and easily breakable. It was statistically proved that *Cliona vermifera* infested living coral at least twice more often than rubble. Although a significant increase of infestation incidence was detected in 2008 by a 2-way ANOVA, relative to 2007 and 2010, a progressive increase in infestation of living coral cannot be reliably concluded in the long run. By considering some information available for the years 2005 and 2006, a worrying trend depicting a progressive increase of infestation from 2005 to 2009 emerges at the first sight (Fig. 1b). Nevertheless, when this trend was analyzed by a one-way ANOVA, differences from year to year in the percentage of infestation of living corals did not result statistically significant, suggesting no substantial shift, in global terms, in the aggressiveness of the sponge against living corals during recent years. Nevertheless, as the power of the one-way ANOVA (5%) fell far below the optimal value (> 80%), conclusive statements cannot be derived at the current time; a longer monitoring time with higher replication effort will be necessary to come up with a definitive conclusion. The reason for the detected decrease of the infestation incidence percentage in both living coral and rubble between 2008 and 2010 remain unknown (Fig. 1a-b). We hope the data provided in this study will serve as a base reference for future monitoring.

At the population level, the sponge reproductive output was substantial, with 60 to 85% of the population producing sexual propagules at a density of 3.5 oocytes per mm² of tissue in at least two reproductive pulses each year. Measured oocyte densities in *C. vermifera* fell within the range of those

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3 known for other oviparous sponge species, often reported to average between 2 and 7 oocytes mm²
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5 (Riesgo and Maldonado 2008). The main difference is that other studied clionids, most of them from
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7 temperate areas, produce only a single, highly synchronic reproductive pulse a year. The results also
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9 confirm that *Cliona vermifera* is gonochoristic, a sex condition contrasting with that of others clionids,
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11 such as *C. viridis* and *C. celata*, which are hermaphroditic (Mariani et al. 2001; Piscitelli et al. 2011).
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13 The abundance of females over males (about 3:1 or higher) is another factor that may help increase the
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15 reproductive output of *C. vermifera*, since a single male is able to fertilize the oocytes of many females.
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17 The synchronous development of gametes in females is consistent with the development pattern noticed
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19 for spermatid cysts, which rapidly became mature when oocytes reached maximum density and
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21 diameter, a synchronic coupling also reported in hermaphroditic *Cliona* spp. (Piscitelli et al. 2011).
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23 Interestingly, the reproductive strategy of *Cliona vermifera* differs from that of viviparous sponges; the
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25 latter ones are often hermaphroditic, experience internal fertilization, and brood large embryos to finally
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27 release swimming larvae at moderate rates over a period lasting from weeks to months (Maldonado
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29 2006; Maldonado and Riesgo 2008). Eggs of sponges with external development, as in *C. vermifera*, are
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31 often substantially smaller, therefore able to be produced at higher densities than brooded eggs.
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33 Nevertheless, the reproduction in *C. vermifera* also differs from the typical reproductive pattern of
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35 oviparous sponges, which are often gonochoric and release a single annual pulse of small eggs to the
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37 water to be fertilized externally (Maldonado and Riesgo 2008, 2009; Riesgo and Maldonado 2008;
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39 Maldonado 2009). All clionids are known to retain mature oocytes within their body for a couple of
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41 days to be fertilized internally (Maldonado and Riesgo 2008; Piscitelli et al. 2011). In the case of *C.*
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43 *vermifera*, mature oocytes were only observed in areas close to exhalant channels, suggesting a previous
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45 migration through the mesohyl towards the excurrent canals for imminent fertilization and release, a
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3 process previously reported in oviparous sponges, such as *Petrosia ficiformis* (Maldonado and Riesgo
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5 2009).
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8 The reproduction strategy of *C. vermifera* appears to incorporate and combine some of the
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10 advantages of viviparous and oviparous sponges. The internal fertilization probably enhances the
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12 likelihood of fertilization success relative to that of purely viviparous species that expel their mature
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14 eggs for a more hazardous fertilization in the water column. Yet it benefits from the high oocyte
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16 densities attained by strictly oviparous species. Likewise, unlike oviparous sponges, *C. vermifera* is able
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18 to protect the more sensitive, early embryonic stages within a capsule (unique among the Porifera),
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20 which probably enhances the survival of the early embryos. This combination of features during the
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22 reproductive process of *C. vermifera*, in addition to its individual abundance in reefs, a female-biased
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24 sex ratio, and several annual reproductive pulses, makes the sponge a tough "plague" for living corals of
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26 the genus *Pocillopora* in Mexican Pacific reefs.
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32 Several environmental parameters have been suggested to be involved in the regulation of
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34 sponge reproductive cycles, including seawater temperature, photoperiods, and lunar phases (Fromont
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36 and Bergquist 1994; Abdo et al. 2008; Maldonado and Riesgo 2008; Riesgo and Maldonado 2008). Of
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38 these environmental factors, water temperature is the most commonly studied. In *Cliona vermifera*, both
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40 gamete density and developmental rates increased substantially with an increase in water temperature
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42 during the yearly thermal cycle, reaching maximum values in summer. It has been repeatedly reported
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44 that after massive bleaching events, the abundance of boring sponges increases substantially (Rützler
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46 2002; Schönberg and Wilkinson 2001; Schönberg and Ortiz 2008; Carballo et al. 2013). The reef system
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48 under study has suffered several bleaching events, being El Niño 1982 probably the most important in
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50 terms of losses of coral cover (Nava and Carballo 2013). Subsequent bleaching events in the study area,
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52 including one triggered by an increase of 1.5°C over the standard average for 6 weeks during the
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3 summer of 2009 that bleached 100% of the coral cover, are thought to stress corals and render them
4 more sensible to disease and infestations (Campos Vazquez 2012). Interestingly, this anomalous
5 increase of water temperatures in 2009 favored a massive coral bleaching in the study area, without
6 apparently altering the reproductive timing and output in the population of *C. vermifera*. The common
7 occurrence of *C. vermifera* in coral reef from the eastern Pacific has been attributed to the sponge ability
8 to infest a variety of calcareous substrata and to thrive in a wide range of microhabitats (Carballo et al.
9 2008, 2013). Because *C. vermifera* is already affecting about 37 % of living *Pocillopora* colonies and
10 because of the enormous reproductive potential of this sponge, any factor negatively affecting the
11 calcification rate of corals (e.g., thermal stress, acidification, pollution, etc) but not the reproductive and
12 growth rates of the tougher *C. vermifera*, may rapidly lead to an imbalance in the coral-sponge
13 relationship and becoming a new threat to Mexican Pacific coral reefs.
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5 Figure 1. a) Differences in average (\pm SD) infestation (%) of *Cliona vermifera* as a function of substratum (living coral = LC, coral rubble= RC) and year. Data for 2007, 2008 and 2010 were analyzed by a 2-way ANOVA and posteriori Holm-Sidak tests, revealing that average infestation of living corals was significantly higher than that of rubble ($p < 0.001$). Time factor was also significant ($p = 0.015$), revealing in 2008 higher infestation than that in 2007 and 2010, which were not significant from each other. In the upper right corner of the graph are summarized the results of the a posteriori tests associated to the ANOVA. Levels of each factors are listed in increasing magnitude, with levels sharing underline being not significantly different from each other. Not regular, initial observations during 2005 and 2006 (referred to as "< 2007" in the graph) were not submitted to analyses but included in the graph as a mere point to indicate an approximate value of infestation in the period prior to the initiation of the current study. b) Average (\pm SD) of infestation (%) of living coral over the period 2005-2010 estimated from monthly averages for each year. The number within the columns indicate the number of months a year with available results. When these data were analyzed by a 1-way ANOVA, between-year differences were found to be non-significant. Nevertheless, the low power of this test (5%) due to unequal, low replication, along with the increasing pattern depicted from 2005 to 2008, alert about the need to establish a long-term monitoring program of coral infestation.

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24 Fig.2. Monthly percentage (%) of *Cliona vermifera* individuals bearing oocytes (O), spermatocysts (SC), or no reproductive elements (NR) over a four year period. Sea surface temperature is represented by the line.

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27 Fig.3. Mean density (\pm SD) of reproductive elements in the tissue of *Cliona vermifera* ($n=25$ samples per month). O, oocytes; SC, spermatocysts; Z, zygotes. Sea surface temperature ($T^{\circ}\text{C}$) is represented by the dashed line.

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30 Fig.4. Mean diameter (\pm SD) of reproductive elements in the tissue of *Cliona vermifera* ($n=25$ samples per month). O, oocytes; SC, spermatocysts; Z, zygotes. Sea surface temperature ($T^{\circ}\text{C}$) is represented by the dashed line.

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34 Fig.5. Histological views of the excavating sponge *Cliona vermifera*. a) Transversal section of a branch of *Pocillopora damicornis* coral heavily infested by *C. vermifera*. b-c) Fragment of coral branch showing the mesohyl of a *C. vermifera* female packed with nearly mature oocytes. d) Cytological section of the sponge mesohyl showing mature oocytes with a nucleolated (nl) nucleus (nu) and abundant yolk granules in the cytoplasm. e) Section of a mature male showing spermatocysts scattered in the mesohyl. f) SEM micrograph showing a spermatocyst with spermatozoa becoming mature synchronously and the flagella oriented towards the lumen of the cyst. g) Detail of a spermatozoon. h) Section of a recently fertilized oocyte (i.e., zygote) while still in the mesohyl, showing its characteristic conspicuous capsule-like envelope (en).

Figure 1. A) Differences in average (\pm SD) infestation (%) of *Cliona vermifera* as a function of substratum (living coral = LC, coral rubble = RC) and year. Data for 2007, 2008 and 2010 were analyzed by a 2-way ANOVA and posteriori Holm-Sidak tests, revealing that average infestation of living corals was significantly higher than that of rubble ($p < 0.001$). Time factor was also significant ($p = 0.015$), revealing in 2008 higher infestation than that in 2007 and 2010, which were not significant from each other. In the upper right corner of the graph are summarized the results of the aposteriori tests associated to the ANOVA. Levels of each factor are listed in increasing magnitude, with levels sharing underline being not significantly different from each other. Not regular, initial observations during 2005 and 2006 (referred to as "< 2007" in the graph) were not submitted to analyses but included in the graph as a mere point to indicate an approximate value of infestation in the period prior to the initiation of the current study. B) Average (\pm SD) of infestation (%) of living coral over the period 2005-2010 estimated from monthly averages for each year. The number within the columns indicate the number of months a year with available results. When these data were analyzed by a 1-way ANOVA, between-year differences were found to be non-significant. Nevertheless, the low power of this test (5%) due to unequal, low replication, along with the increasing pattern depicted from 2005 to 2008, alert about the need to establish a long-term monitoring program of coral infestation.

72x31mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 2. Monthly percentage (%) of *Cliona vermifera* individuals bearing oocytes (O), spermatocysts (SC), or no reproductive elements (NR) over a four year period. Sea surface temperature is represented by the line.

116x65mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Review

Figure 3. Mean density (\pm SD) of reproductive elements in the tissue of *Cliona vermifera* ($n=25$ samples per month). O, oocytes; SC, spermatic cysts; Z, zygotes. Sea surface temperature (T °C) is represented by the dashed line.

111x59mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 4. Mean diameter (\pm SD) of reproductive elements in the tissue of *Cliona vermifera* (n=25 samples per month). O, oocytes; SC, spermatic cysts; Z, zygotes. Sea surface temperature (T °C) is represented by the dashed line.

111x59mm (300 x 300 DPI)

Figure 5. Histological views of the excavating sponge *Cliona vermifera*. A) Transversal section of a branch of *Pocillopora damicornis* coral heavily infested by *C. vermifera*. B-C) Fragment of coral branch showing the mesohyl of a *C. vermifera* female packed with nearly mature oocytes. D) Cytological section of the sponge mesohyl showing mature oocytes with a nucleolated (nl) nucleus (nu) and abundant yolk granules in the cytoplasm. E) Section of a mature male showing spermatic cysts scattered in the mesohyl. F) SEM micrograph showing a spermatic cyst with spermatozoa becoming mature synchronously and the flagella oriented towards the lumen of the cyst. G) Detail of a spermatozoon. H) Section of a recently fertilized oocyte (i.e., zygote) while still in the mesohyl, showing its characteristic conspicuous capsule-like envelope (en).

190x219mm (300 x 300 DPI)